

Enhancing Student Engagement and Learning Outcomes Through Live Marking and Socrative: A Formative Assessment Study in Secondary Science Classrooms

Excel Obumneme Amaefule ✉

SOAS, University of London, WC1H 0XG, 10 Thornhaugh St, London, United Kingdom;
University of Birmingham, Edgbaston Birmingham, B15 2TT, United Kingdom;
Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, 440101, Abia, Nigeria

Abstract

This study investigates the effectiveness of two formative assessment strategies—live marking and Socrative—in enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes in secondary science classrooms. Conducted in a Birmingham academy school, the study responds to the increasing demand for assessment tools that provide real-time feedback and support responsive teaching. Using a case study design and an interpretivist paradigm, data were gathered from teacher interviews, student questionnaires, classroom observations, and field notes. Thematic and graphical analysis revealed that live marking fostered immediate feedback, improved student motivation, and supported differentiation, particularly for SEND students. Socrative's real-time data visualisation encouraged self-assessment and active participation, although challenges such as screen fatigue and distractions were noted. Despite time and resource constraints, triangulating feedback from teachers, students, and observations ensured robust insights. The study concludes that these AfL techniques, when implemented thoughtfully, foster inclusive, data-informed teaching that enhances science learning. Implications include the need for balanced integration of digital and traditional tools, tailored feedback strategies, and teacher training to optimise impact. The findings offer practical guidance for science educators aiming to refine formative assessment practices.

Keywords: *Formative assessment, Live Marking, Socrative, Student engagement, science education.*

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Introduction

Over the years, assessment studies have evolved from traditional test formats toward exploring the relationship between assessment and classroom learning. This shift reflects growing optimism that improving classroom assessment practices can significantly enhance learning (Black and William, 1998). Assessment in science is a broad practice that evaluates student learning and understanding, emphasising fostering learning through engagement in the assessment process (National Research Council, 2001).

Assessment for Learning and Assessment of Learning

Authors like Black and Wiliam (1998) acknowledge that formative assessment (or Assessment for Learning, AfL) lacks strict definitions but is generally viewed as a dynamic, interactive strategy used by teachers and students to provide feedback, enhance student learning, and inform teaching practices (Black and Wiliam, 2010, p. 82; Dixson and Worrell, 2016; Stanja et al., 2023). Black and Harrison (2004) define formative assessment as “any assessment for which the priority in its design and practice is to serve the purpose of promoting pupils’ learning.” (Black and Harrison, 2004, p. 1; Gioka, 2007, p. 113). Wolterinck et al. (2024, p. 711) emphasise that effective implementation of AfL requires teachers to develop specific competencies, including the ability to collect, analyse, and interpret assessment data, which are crucial for adapting instruction to meet diverse student needs. This highlights how targeted professional development programs are critical for equipping teachers with skills to integrate AfL strategies and enhance student outcomes.

Black and Wiliam (1998) emphasised that formative assessment, which consists of a wide range of tools, as seen in Fig. 1, goes beyond adding exercises; it requires a fundamental shift in classroom pedagogy. Effective AfL practices, especially those focusing on self-assessment and constructive feedback, can significantly enhance student motivation and self-perception, leading to improved learning outcomes. Cowie and Bell (1999) identify two types of formative assessment: planned and interactive. Planned formative assessment involves teachers systematically eliciting, interpreting, and acting on assessment information with the whole class, whereas interactive AfL occurs during student-teacher interactions, allowing teachers to recognise and respond to individual needs in real-time. Dixson and Worrell (2016) similarly describe two AfL types—spontaneous and planned. Spontaneous assessments happen in realtime, through questioning and observing body language, while planned assessments include structured activities like quizzes to monitor progress. Both Cowie and Bell’s interactive assessment and Dixson and Worrell’s spontaneous assessment emphasise real-time interactions, highlighting a shared recognition of the need for structured and responsive strategies in effective formative assessment practices.

In contrast, summative assessment (or Assessment of Learning (AoL)) typically evaluates student learning after an instructional period, often assigning grades or certifying achievement. The National Research Council (2001, p. 25) defines summative assessment as “cumulative assessments [...] that intend to capture what a student has learned, or the quality of the learning, and judge performance against some standards” (see also Dixson and Worrell, 2016, p. 156). As shown in Fig. 1, it is generally high-stakes, formal, and measures what students have learned by the end of a course. The National Research Council (2001) critiques traditional summative assessments for prioritising selection and accountability over improved learning outcomes. Common issues include "teaching to the test," lack of timing for remediation, limited detailed feedback (especially in machine-based marking), and a narrow assessment scope, underscoring the need for formative assessments that provide actionable insights to support student learning effectively. AfL has evolved from rigid, test-based methods to more flexible approaches that facilitate interaction between classroom learning and assessment (Black and Wiliam, 1998). However, it is recommended that AfL and AoL work in tandem to optimize learning outcomes, with AfL guiding the learning process and AoL serving as checkpoints or milestones (National Research Council, 2001; Dixson and Worrell, 2016). The shift towards formative assessment gained momentum with the No Child Left Behind Act (2002), which emphasized accountability and equitable educational opportunities, particularly for disadvantaged groups, through transparent and supportive learning approaches. The authors highlight that Assessment for Learning (AfL) surpasses Assessment of Learning (AoL) by offering constructive feedback tailored to individual or class learning needs, whereas AoL often leads to comparisons among students both within and outside institutions. Unlike AoL, which primarily measures learning, AfL actively supports and promotes it (Black and Wiliam, 1998).

Characteristics of Formative and Summative Assessments

<i>Characteristic</i>	<i>Formative Assessment</i>	<i>Summative Assessment</i>
Purpose	To improve teaching and learning To diagnose student difficulties	Evaluation of learning outcomes Placement, promotion decisions
Formality	Usually informal	Usually formal
Timing of administration	Ongoing, before and during instruction	Cumulative, after instruction
Developers	Classroom teachers to test publishers	Classroom teachers to test publishers
Level of stakes	Low-stakes	High-stakes
Psychometric rigor	Low to high	Moderate to High
Types of questions asked	What is working	Does student understand the material
	What needs to be improved	Is the student prepared for next level of activity
	How can it be improved	
Examples	Observations	Projects
	Homework	Performance assessments
	Question and answer sessions	Portfolios
	Self-evaluations	Papers
	Reflections on performance	In-class examinations
	Curriculum-based measures	State and national tests

Figure 1. Showing Summary Characteristics of Formative (AfL) and Summative (AoL) Assessments

Source: Dixson and Worrell, 2016

Challenges of Formative Assessment

Black and William (1998) highlight the potential negative impact of non-constructive feedback and the complexities of creating a classroom culture that supports formative assessment. However, Authors highlight the necessity of professional development for teachers to enhance their understanding of formative assessment practices. Equipping teachers with the skills to deliver effective feedback can mitigate the potential negative impacts of non-constructive feedback (Bennett, 2011). Since "formative assessment" lacks a well-defined set of practices (Black and Wiliam, 1998; Bennett, 2011), this could lead to varied interpretations and implementations across educational contexts, resulting in inconsistent effects on student learning (Bennett, 2011). Authors however, also note that this flexibility also allows teachers to adapt their instructions and feedback interactively to meet pupils' individual and collective learning needs, considering that each student and teacher is unique (Black and Wiliam, 1998, 2010; National Research Council, 2001; Dixson and Worrell, 2016), thereby supporting the No Child Left Behind Act (2002).

Applications of AfL in Science Education

Black and Harrison (2004) argue that science teachers should challenge students with activities that engage them in critical thinking and help them apply scientific knowledge across different contexts. This approach helps teachers assess what students understand in the science classroom and goes beyond simple recall of facts. For example, students can identify similarities and differences across subjects by "comparing ideas about combustion with those of respiration" (Black and Harrison, 2004, p. 5), enhancing their observational skills and deepening their understanding. More recent studies on AfL in science education, such as that by Asyhari et al. (2024), present a compelling investigation into implementing the Feedback Loop Model (FLM) within the AfL framework in high school physics education. Their research demonstrates significant improvements in student engagement and conceptual understanding, especially in areas like kinematics and motion dynamics. The iterative feedback

mechanism, which includes observation, feedback, reflection, and action, allows students to track their progress, overcome conceptual barriers, and engage in active learning. This research highlights the transformative potential of integrating FLM and AfL for fostering deeper understanding and engagement in physics. It suggests that such approaches could have a positive impact on student outcomes across various STEM disciplines.

Goika (2007) emphasised that when science students' strengths and weaknesses were constructively addressed through feedback, their learning improved significantly. Goika's study, which examined nine biology science teachers in Greater London, found that AfL practices among secondary school science teachers were limited at the time (Goika, 2007). More recent studies have highlighted the benefits of increased teacher training—such as the one I am currently pursuing—and school-wide initiatives aimed at promoting AfL strategies (Lysaght, O'Leary, and Ludlow, 2017). This shift may be partially attributed to greater support from educational institutions and government policies (e.g., the No Child Left Behind Policy, 2002). In both the UK and the US, researchers have developed tools like the AfL Audit (AFLAi) and Management Instrument (AfLMi) to help schools evaluate and enhance their existing AfL practices. The results from these studies indicate that certain AfL practices are now more widely adopted than before (Lysaght, O'Leary, and Ludlow, 2017).

AfL Techniques (Live-Marking and Socrative)

Live marking and Socrative are both practical formative assessment tools that can enhance learning, particularly in science education. My justification for choosing these two techniques for this study is firstly due to their prevalence in use by teachers in the school where I am conducting my study. Informal conversation and class observations showed that many teachers favoured live marking as a go-to method to observe classroom activities and learning outcomes, in order to provide scaffold where needed. Most also used socrative as an AfL to assess student understanding and view real-time data with mathematic visualisation to aid them inform their teacher-student learning trajectory. This study's findings will help myself and other teachers and academic body understand these tools' effectiveness in classrooms, thereby improving teaching standards. In a digital learning context, Socrative's utilisation is justified by the institutions' support for iPads and its recognition as a valuable formative assessment tool. However, it is crucial to acknowledge potential challenges, such as distractions stemming from digital devices, which necessitate exploration of Socrative's impact to ascertain its true value in learning compared to its drawbacks. Chalmers, Mowat and Chapman, (2018) highlight the benefits of marking face-to-face/ interactive feedback over traditional written feedback, which may seem "cold" and less engaging for students. This is because feedback in classrooms have been highlighted as very integral to students learning (Elliott, 2022).

Socrative, on the other hand, offers a technology-enhanced solution for formative assessment (see Balta and Tzafilkou, 2019), allowing teachers to administer quizzes, polls, and exit tickets, all of which generate real-time data insights. Although at a tertiary level, studies found through a survey that students highlighted its advantages, including “the practical use, time-saving, immediate feedback and enabling many question types” (Balta and Tzafilkou, 2019, p. 307). Studies highlight its use in increasing student learning enthusiasm, critical thinking and collaboration (Awedh *et al.*, 2015; El Shaban, 2017). Assessing the benefits at a secondary education level would greatly contribute to better teaching practices. Batool *et al.* (2018) and Christianson (2020) emphasise how Socrative's interactive features enhance active learning and engagement in diverse classroom settings, including science and remote learning environments. This underscores its importance in a post-COVID-19 world, where technology shapes remote and in-person education (see Christianson, 2020). Batool *et al.* (2018) found that while undergraduate medical students appreciated Socrative, they were reluctant to abandon paper-based methods entirely. Investigating whether secondary school students share similar views will be part of this study. The study identifies challenges like reliance on technology, screen time discomfort, and application difficulty. However, proper orientation, student support, and combining digital with paper-based assessments may ease the transition (Batool *et al.*, 2018). As highlighted in Figure 1 above, both methods,

which I have chosen, would arguably enable me make observations of students' learning outcomes and reflect in real-time on how to improve and pivot the learning trajectory.

Having stated an overview and justification for the study, it will be guided by the research questions outlined in the methodology section below.

Materials and Methods

This research adopts an interpretivist approach to examine the effectiveness of Assessment for Learning (AfL) strategies in science classrooms, explicitly focusing on live marking and Socratic. The study is confirmatory, following a deductive framework and assessing AfL's effectiveness based on prior research (Taber, 2013, 2020; Hattie and Jaeger, 1998). The study addresses two key questions:

1. How effective is the combination of AfL strategies, such as live marking and Socratic, in enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes in science classrooms?
2. How can teachers implement these strategies to balance engagement, equitable feedback, and minimal disruptions?

Research Design

The study employs a case study methodology chosen for its ability to provide detailed insights into specific educational contexts, such as Year 10 science classrooms in an academy school in Birmingham. This approach captures the dynamics of teacher-student interactions and evaluates AfL strategies' impact (Swanborn, 2010; Hancock, Algozzine, & Lim, 2021; White & Cooper, 2022). Although case studies are limited by their lack of generalisability and potential researcher bias, they offer rich, context-specific understanding that can inform future educational practices.

Sampling Strategy

A non-probability convenience sampling method was employed to recruit participants for this study, reflecting both accessibility and relevance to the research aims. The sample comprised three experienced science teachers, each with between 3 and 20 years of teaching experience, and a Year 10 science class consisting of 31 students. This cohort was purposefully selected to ensure diversity in academic attainment levels, including high-, medium-, and low-attaining pupils, as well as those identified with Special Educational Needs and Disabilities (SEND). Of the 31 students, 23 voluntarily participated in the questionnaire phase of the study.

Data were collected in a cross-sectional format between 19 November and 15 December 2024. Formative assessment strategies, specifically live marking and Socratic, were implemented during various topics, with student survey responses collected during a Year 10 lesson on "What are renewable energy resources?", delivered during the final period (Period 5) of a school day (15th December 2024).

In addition to the student questionnaires administered via Socratic, the data set included qualitative evidence from classroom observations and teacher interviews. Observations were conducted across both Year 7 and Year 10 science classes over three consecutive weeks to assess the impact of AfL strategies across different key stage levels. Teacher interviews and surveys were conducted either in person or via email, depending on the participants' preferences. This multi-stakeholder approach provided a robust, triangulated dataset, contributing to data adequacy and thematic saturation (Nwozor et al., 2021).

Research Ethics

BERA, (2018), and The University of Birmingham's Data Protection and Ethics Guidelines were followed and researcher received ethics approval on November 19, 2024. Participants or their guardians/parents provided oral and documented consent using an "Opt out" system, and confidentiality was maintained through anonymisation, with an option to withdraw at any time (see Appendix Section

A for all copies of ethics and consent form. This will include ethics form, headteacher, teacher, and guardian consent samples or forms).

Data Analysis

Qualitative data from interviews and observations were analysed using manual thematic analysis and NVivo software, allowing for systematic coding into themes. Quantitative data from Socrative were analysed graphically and interpreted by the researcher to identify patterns in student engagement and feedback quality.

Limitations and Practical Constraints

This study was constrained by time and resources, restricting data collection to a cross-sectional design rather than a longitudinal study across key stages. However, the inclusion of diverse data sources—teacher and student perspectives, classroom observations, and quantitative analysis—provides a robust foundation for evaluating AfL strategies.

Results

Thematic Analysis of Teacher Responses

The thematic analysis of teacher responses provided valuable insights into their perceptions and experiences with Assessment for Learning (AfL) techniques, particularly live marking and Socrative, in science education. Several themes emerged from the data, highlighting the critical role of AfL in supporting student learning, informing teaching practices, and addressing key challenges.

General Views on Assessment for Learning

Teachers unanimously agreed that AfL is pivotal in fostering student engagement and supporting their academic progress. The responses emphasised that AfL is a foundational tool to identify learning gaps and misconceptions while informing teaching strategies. Participant 1 reflected this by stating, *“AfL is essential in identifying any misconceptions students may have when tackling new topics or lessons... Addressing these misconceptions early is crucial.”* This view illustrates how AfL enables teachers to identify patterns, intervene promptly and guide students toward a clearer understanding of the subject matter. Participant 2 further elaborated on the utility of AfL in shaping teaching priorities, noting, *“AfL continuously informs teaching to ensure both the teacher and students are aware of their learning progress. Then, teaching can be prioritised, stretched, or further scaffolded to support students.”* This adaptive approach ensures that teaching is responsive to the needs of all learners, particularly those who require additional support. Similarly, Participant 3 highlighted the role of AfL in decision-making, stating, *“Without AfL, how can the teacher decide to move on or re-teach misconceptions?”* Collectively, these responses underscore the integral role of AfL in creating a dynamic, student-centered learning environment.

Justification for Using Live Marking

Live marking emerged as a widely valued AfL technique, with teachers highlighting its effectiveness in providing immediate feedback and fostering student accountability. Participant 1 explained, *“Live marking provides a snapshot of students’ understanding during the lesson... It motivates them to engage more as they realise their progress is being monitored.”* This perspective reflects the motivational aspect of live marking, which encourages active participation and enhances student focus and self-awareness. Another significant advantage of live marking is its real-time ability to identify and address misconceptions. Participant 3 noted, *“Live marking reduces the chances of whole areas of the scheme of work being poorly attempted in summative assessments.”* By intervening promptly, teachers can ensure students develop a solid understanding of foundational concepts, reducing the risk of cumulative knowledge gaps. The technique also proved beneficial for supporting students with special educational needs and disabilities (SEND). Participant 1 shared, *“I prioritise them [SEND students] when live marking, ensuring they understand expectations by asking them to*

repeat instructions.” This individualised approach highlights the inclusive potential of live marking in catering to diverse learner needs.

Justification for Using Socrative

Teachers also spoke highly of Socrative, emphasising its utility as a digital tool for tracking student progress and facilitating formative assessment. Participant 1 described the platform’s ability to provide instant feedback: *“Socrative is an excellent tool for exit tasks, which we use as multiple-choice quizzes with three questions and options. It provides instant class-wide data, showing percentages of correct answers per question. If a question has less than an 80% success rate, I incorporate it into the next lesson’s starter task to reteach the concept.”* Participant 2 described the platform’s ability to check if learning outcomes match objectives and also instant feedback and pattern recognition: *“...we tend to use it at the end of the lesson as an instant multi-choice checking three of the core learning objectives. Students get instant feedback about whether they are right or wrong... Patterns can then be spotted in students’ answers to address misconceptions.”* This real-time data analysis enables teachers to identify trends and adapt their instruction accordingly.

The capacity of Socrative to track individual student progress was another key benefit. Participant 1 remarked, *“Socrative also tracks engagement, allowing teachers to see who has completed the task in real-time,... and ensures they stay on track.”* This feature not only enhances classroom management but also promotes accountability among students. Additionally, integrating Socrative into students’ iPads was seen as an opportunity to develop their digital literacy. Participant 1 observed, *“As a digital tool integrated into students’ iPads, Socrative enhances their IT literacy while engaging them with user-friendly tasks.”* This dual benefit of supporting learning while fostering technological skills highlights the versatility of Socrative in modern classrooms. Participant 3 mentioned he rarely uses Socrative as an AfL, stating, *“As I rarely use Socrative, I cannot comment.”* Participants further highlighted how digital tools like Socrative reduce excuses or barriers to participation. P2 highlights that *“the students are noticeably more engaged with Socrative rather than writing in their books.”*

Impact on Student Learning

Both live marking and Socrative were credited with significantly enhancing student engagement and understanding. Participant 1 reflected on the impact of live marking on motivation and self-awareness, stating, *“Live marking helps students see their progress and feel a sense of achievement, building intrinsic motivation.”* he also stated, *“This visibility encourages students to take responsibility for their work and ensures they stay on track.... They can review their answers and seek clarification. This self-awareness encourages them to address their learning gaps proactively, either individually or with teacher support.”* This sense of accomplishment encourages students to take ownership of their learning journey. Similarly, Socrative was found to foster a competitive yet collaborative classroom environment. Participant 2 shared, *“Students are keen to get 3/3 on Socrative and will be competitive with each other.”* This friendly competition not only drives engagement but also reinforces knowledge retention. Furthermore, Socrative's ability to highlight learning gaps was seen as a critical advantage. Participant 1 noted, *“Socrative provides data that guides follow-up lessons, ensuring gaps in understanding are addressed.”* These observations demonstrate how both techniques contribute to a more targeted and effective learning process.

Impact on Teaching Practices

The use of AfL techniques also had a profound impact on teachers’ instructional strategies, prompting more responsive and data-driven approaches. Participant 1 highlighted how Socrative and live-marking supports lesson planning and teacher-student interaction, stating, *“Socrative helps me adapt my lesson planning based on data, ensuring I address areas of weakness.”* Also, *“Live marking improves my interactions with students, as I provide immediate feedback and create small interventions when needed.”* This adaptability ensures that teaching is tailored to the evolving classroom needs and helps build stronger relationships and personalised support.

Challenges in Implementing AfL Techniques

Despite their numerous benefits, live marking and Socratic posed specific challenges that teachers had to navigate. For instance, the potential for disruption during live marking was a concern teachers must consider. Participant 1 explained, *“The feedback is minimal—quick and snappy—so it shouldn’t disrupt the students too much...If they’ve got the answer right, I’ll tick it because students appreciate that positive reassurance. If they need help, I provide quick feedback, either verbal or written, usually just one word or a short phrase to prompt further thinking.”* This careful balancing act requires teachers to provide meaningful feedback without interrupting the flow of the lesson.

Time efficiency was another challenge, particularly when comparing verbal and written feedback. Participant 2 noted that they did not see this as an issue, *“I do not tend to find this to be an issue in science...I find that verbal feedback when students are struggling is much more time-efficient than live marking using written feedback.”* Also, the need for strategic planning to ensure equitable student attention, particularly in addressing the needs of SEND students, was raised. Participant 3 highlighted how these challenges have influenced their teaching practice and lesson structure. They explained, *“I plan to have large units of time given over to ‘independent’ tasks so that I can live mark. During the ‘engage’ phases, I tend to go to the SEND pupils because of time restrictions...Yes, I agree that some pupils are stopped, but the benefits outweigh the demerits.”* Here, participants highlight the importance of understanding trade-offs and selecting the most appropriate feedback method based on the context and student needs. In the case of Socratic, issues such as copying and misuse of digital tools were raised. Participant 3 cautioned, *“Socratic gives a snapshot of pupil understanding, although this should be tempered with the accusation that pupils sometimes copy each other’s answers.”* According to the participants, these concerns highlight the need for robust strategies to ensure the integrity and effectiveness of digital assessment tools.

Teacher responses provide insights into how AfL techniques like live marking and Socratic influence teaching practices and student learning. To complement these perspectives, the following section examines findings from student questionnaires, offering a comparative lens to evaluate the effectiveness and reception of these techniques from the learners' point of view.

Discussion

Thematic Analysis of Student Responses

1. Live marking helped me understand my mistakes and improve my work immediately

Figure 2. Likert Scale Responses Showing Students’ Perceptions of Real-Time Feedback from Live Marking

2. Using Socrative made learning more interactive and engaging.

Figure 3. Likert Scale Responses Illustrating Students' Perceptions of Socrative's Ability to Enhance Interactivity and Engagement in Learning

3. I prefer working on my Ipad and using socrative to independent tasks over writing on paper.

Figure 4. Likert Scale Results Showing a Divide in Student Preferences for Digital Tools Versus Traditional Methods

4. I found it easier to learn when feedback was immediate (e.g., live marking or Socrative).

Figure 5. Percentage of Students Reporting Ease of Learning Because of Immediate Feedback from Livemarking and Socrative

5. AfL techniques used in class motivated me to participate more.

Figure 6. Percentage of Students Reporting Increased Motivation and Participation due to Formative Assessment Techniques

Analysis

The findings from the Likert scale responses (Figures 2–6) and open-ended questions (Tables 1–3) provide a nuanced understanding of students' perceptions of formative assessment techniques, particularly live marking and Socrative. The results highlight both the strengths and challenges associated with these methods, offering insights into real-time feedback, interactivity, digital vs. traditional preferences, and motivation.

Real-Time Feedback

From the data, a significant majority (88%) of students strongly agreed or agreed that live marking helped them identify and correct their mistakes during lessons (Figure 2). Students valued the immediacy of this feedback, with one remarking, *"I like that I can fix my mistakes straight away."* Another said, *"So I know where I went wrong and can ask straight away."* However, some students expressed reservations, with 8% remaining neutral and 4% disagreeing. This group raised concerns about the clarity and delivery of feedback. For instance, one student remarked, *"Sometimes, it can be too quick,"* and another stated, *"Having a question that didn't specify that two answers were supposed to be correct, so I then ticked one, but my answer was deduced as wrong."*

Increased Interactivity with Digital Tools

The integration of Socrative was widely praised for enhancing classroom interactivity, with 91% of students agreeing or strongly agreeing that it made learning more engaging (Figure 3). Many students highlighted the gamified elements of Socrative, describing it as *"its fun because you get to test yourself"* and appreciating how it transformed quizzes into a dynamic part of their learning.

Nonetheless, a small minority (4% neutral and 4% disagreed) expressed concerns about the tool's effectiveness. These students cited issues like screen fatigue and difficulty maintaining focus during prolonged use. One commented, *"It's hard to focus on the screen for too long."* This highlights the need for balanced integration of digital tools, with consideration for students who may struggle with extended screen time. These findings suggest that while digital tools can enhance engagement, they must be implemented thoughtfully, with considerations for varying student needs and potential drawbacks.

Preference for Digital vs. Traditional Methods

The results revealed a divide in student preferences for digital versus traditional learning approaches. While 79% of students preferred using iPads and Socrative over paper-based methods (Figure 4), a notable minority (16% neutral or disagreed) favoured traditional tools. Advocates for digital tools emphasised their efficiency and convenience, with one student stating, *“Using iPads is quicker than writing”* and another, *“it’s easier and quicker as the teacher can take time to explain when some students do not get it without us wasting time on book.”* Conversely, students favouring traditional methods highlighted the benefits of handwriting for memory retention and comprehension. One student reflected, *“I find writing on paper helps me remember better.”* These divergent views underscore the importance of offering a balanced approach that accommodates diverse learning styles and preferences within the classroom.

Impact of Immediate Feedback

The role of immediate feedback in facilitating learning was evident in the data, with 76% of students agreeing or strongly agreeing that such feedback made learning easier (Figure 5). One student observed, *“...I get my result immediately. I find it helps when I get my result or feedback straight away.”* another stated, *“So I know where I went wrong and can ask straight away.”* A third wrote, *“It allows me to know my mistakes quickly and take corrections.”* However, a substantial portion of students (20% neutral, 4% disagreed) expressed mixed feelings about the immediacy of feedback. This group may benefit from delayed reflection or additional support to process feedback effectively as one student explained, *“I sometimes need more time to think about what I did wrong.”*

Motivation and Participation

The motivational impact of formative assessment techniques was a recurring theme. Approximately 74% of students felt motivated by these methods, citing the competitive and interactive nature of tools like Socrative (Figure 6). One student stated, *“Knowing I’ll get feedback pushes me to try harder,”* while another described the excitement of achieving high scores in Socrative quizzes as *“fun and encouraging.”* One mentioned how it motivates them to revise, stating, *“can go back to what lessons I’ve done.”*

Yet, motivation was not universal, with 26% of students remaining neutral about its impact, mentioning how getting wrong answers make them feel publicly. One student noted, *“Feedback doesn’t always motivate me—it depends on the subject.”* and another noted *“Public embarrassment.”* This suggests that task design and subject relevance play a critical role in leveraging formative assessment techniques to boost engagement.

Suggestions for Improvement

Students offered a variety of suggestions to enhance AfL and improve learning outcomes, emphasising the integration of technology, interactive activities, and additional support. Many students highlighted the value of digital tools, suggesting more frequent use of iPads, laptops, and videos in the classroom. As one student remarked, *“Using the iPad frequently”* would make lessons more engaging, while another noted, *“Like videos and stuff.”* Interactive and hands-on activities were also widely recommended to better understand complex concepts. One student explained, *“Personally, I find things easier to understand when it’s more hands-on. I struggle to understand when it’s being explained.”* Practical tasks, such as *“doing exam-style questions,”* were specifically mentioned for their ability to foster deeper comprehension. Additionally, students expressed a need for supplementary resources and tailored support. Suggestions included *“more quizzes,”* *“theory-focused Socrative sessions,”* and *“extra one-to-one support.”* These responses reflect a desire for diverse tools and personalised attention to reinforce understanding and support individual learning needs.

Field Observations: Use of Live Marking and Socrative

The field observations of a year 7 and year 10 class revealed that live marking effectively enhanced student engagement, strengthened teacher-student relationships, and enabled immediate correction of misconceptions. Students responded positively, seeking feedback and showing motivation through

incentives like "good" ticks, which improved participation and behaviour. Socrative complemented this by providing real-time assessment and fostering active participation through gamified elements, allowing targeted reteaching based on instant data. However, challenges such as time management, digital distractions (e.g., games on iPads), and reduced writing habits were noted. These were mitigated by prioritising key students during live marking, using monitoring tools like Apple Classroom to prevent distractions, and implementing "no-opt-out" writing policies for essential tasks. These tools showed significantly improved engagement and understanding when thoughtfully integrated into lessons (see appendix section B for complete field observations, and other relevant data).

Addressing Research Questions

This study provides a nuanced understanding of how formative assessment techniques, specifically live marking and Socrative, enhance student engagement and learning outcomes in secondary science classrooms. By addressing the research questions, the findings reveal these tool's effectiveness and offer practical insights into implementing them in my teaching practice.

Addressing Research Question 1: Effectiveness of AfL Techniques

The findings demonstrate that formative assessment techniques like Socrative and live marking effectively enhance motivation, engagement, and learning outcomes for most students. However, addressing the minority who benefit less highlights the importance of teachers understanding classroom dynamics and applying feedback strategically. Variations in motivation across science subjects suggest that AfL tools' effectiveness depends on alignment with subject-specific demands and task relevance. Task irrelevance was also cited as a demotivating factor, emphasising the need for assessments to align with clear learning objectives and demonstrate value to students.

Live marking enables teachers to better understand their classrooms by fostering relationships through small interactions, which can then be leveraged to provide personalised support for students across different attainment levels. Challenges of live marking disrupting students focused on writing and ensuring equitable teacher attention, as noted by Simmons (2019) and students, were addressed through various adaptations. Teachers timed interventions strategically, provided concise feedback, and incorporated independent tasks to allow circulation and balanced support. Live marking was also effective in identifying disengaged and quieter students, ensuring their needs were met. Similarly, Socrative's low-risk, non-permanent nature encouraged participation, particularly among less engaged students, and enhanced learning outcomes. Findings show public feedback, though valuable, can risk embarrassing students, particularly in group settings. Balancing public with private feedback mechanisms can mitigate this issue. Teachers emphasised the importance of clear, dynamic feedback, with live marking fostering active participation by addressing misconceptions in real time. Students (91%) reported feeling motivated, likely due to Socrative's immediate corrections or gamification, reflecting its inclusivity and ability to cater to diverse learning preferences. Additionally, these tools foster academic and digital literacy, along with collaborative behaviours, supporting key modern competencies.

Overall, despite some nuances, the results affirm the argument on the effectiveness of combining AfL strategies like Socrative and live marking in meeting diverse learning needs, aligning with my observations and Chalmers, Mowat, and Chapman's (2018) findings.

Adaptations and Benefits of Live Marking

Teachers demonstrated that live marking encourages active participation by providing real-time feedback that addresses misconceptions promptly. This approach fosters stronger teacher-student relationships, which can be leveraged to offer personalised support. Live marking also proved instrumental in identifying disengaged students and ensuring that quieter individuals received the attention they needed.

Observations show that students were more willing to raise their hands and seek help when teachers employed live marking, which created a low-risk environment for participation.

Nevertheless, challenges such as disruptions to students focused on writing and equitable teacher attention were identified, aligning with Simmons' (2019) findings. Teachers mitigated these issues by adopting strategic approaches, such as timing interventions carefully, providing concise and targeted feedback, and incorporating sufficient independent work periods. This structure allowed teachers to circulate the classroom effectively, balancing support among all students, including those with SEND or lower attainment levels.

The Role of Socrative in Enhancing Engagement

Socrative's interactive and gamified features contributed significantly to motivation and engagement, particularly among students who are typically less active. Its low-risk, non-permanent nature encouraged these students to participate more readily. Teachers highlighted how Socrative's instant feedback and trend analysis enabled them to focus on explanations and reteaching, enhancing their ability to address learning gaps efficiently.

While Socrative offered substantial benefits, minor drawbacks such as screen fatigue and distractions were noted, reflecting the need for balanced use of digital tools. Public feedback through Socrative quizzes, while motivating for many, alienated some students who preferred private corrections. These observations point to the importance of tailoring formative assessment methods to individual and classroom needs.

Addressing Literature Gaps

The study also addresses gaps in the literature, particularly the limited exploration of Socrative's application in secondary education compared to higher education contexts. The findings demonstrate how tools like Socrative and live marking not only enhance academic outcomes but also foster skills such as digital literacy and collaborative behaviours—key competencies for modern learners.

This aligns with research by Goika (2007) and Lysaght, O'Leary, and Ludlow (2017), which emphasises the transformative potential of formative assessment when aligned with professional development initiatives. Furthermore, the study corroborates Black and Harrison's (2004) assertion that formative assessment requires a shift in pedagogy, prioritising engagement and constructive feedback.

Challenges and Future Considerations

Despite the overwhelming support for these techniques, a minority of students (4%) expressed concerns about rushed feedback in live marking, while 26% remained neutral regarding Socrative's impact on motivation. These findings highlight the need for thoughtful implementation, ensuring that feedback is clear, timely, and contextually appropriate.

By integrating formative assessment tools like Socrative and live marking, teachers can create inclusive learning environments that cater to diverse needs. However, to optimise their impact, these strategies must be adapted to subject-specific requirements and student preferences. This nuanced approach ensures that formative assessments do not merely deliver feedback but actively support learning across varied educational contexts.

Overall, the findings affirm the effectiveness of combining AfL strategies like live marking and Socrative to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes. These techniques, when implemented thoughtfully and aligned with clear objectives, offer transformative potential for modern classrooms. However, their success depends on the teacher's ability to adapt tools to the unique needs of their students, ensuring that feedback is timely, relevant, and inclusive. This study builds on existing scholarship, reinforcing the importance of formative assessment in fostering dynamic, student-centred learning environments.

Addressing Research Question 2: Strategies for Implementation and Teaching Practice Implications

The study underscores the need for strategic planning and adaptive teaching practices to implement AfL techniques effectively and shows how AfL influences teacher actions and teaching practice. Teachers highlighted the importance of prioritising students with SEND during short tasks, while maintaining balance by structuring longer task-time for whole-class live-marking and behavioural challenges during live marking to ensure equitable attention and minimise disruptions. My observations support this, as early focus on low-ability or disruptive students helped maintain overall class engagement. Positive reinforcement, such as task completion incentives (like positive points), effectively motivates students and improves behaviour.

Socrative's instant feedback was key to data-driven lesson planning, though challenges like time constraints and digital distractions required targeted interventions. Tools like Apple Classroom helped manage screen time and reduce off-task behaviour. The "no-opt-out" writing policy further addressed reduced writing habits, ensuring task completion and flexibility.

These insights will shape my future teaching practice in diverse ways, for example, allocating sufficient time for independent tasks to support effective live marking, and focus on SEND and low-ability students during shorter tasks, and plan for high attaining students who might complete tasks early to minimise disruptions. The findings highlight the importance of balancing digital and traditional methods for diverse student needs and improved learning outcomes.

Conclusion

The findings of this study highlight the transformative potential of formative assessment techniques such as live marking and Socrative in secondary science classrooms. These tools effectively enhance student engagement, intrinsic motivation, and learning outcomes by providing real-time feedback and fostering interactivity. Live marking was particularly impactful in addressing misconceptions promptly and fostering teacher-student relationships that support personalised learning. Similarly, Socrative's gamified, low-risk approach encouraged participation from typically disengaged students, reflecting its inclusivity and adaptability to diverse learning needs.

Despite these strengths, the study acknowledges challenges such as time management, potential disruptions, and digital distractions. However, strategic implementation—such as timing interventions, balancing public and private feedback, and integrating supportive tools like Apple Classroom—can mitigate these issues. The findings also reveal that the effectiveness of these techniques varies across subjects, emphasising the need for alignment with subject-specific demands and task relevance to sustain motivation and engagement. For instance, data-driven tools like Socrative proved more suited to structured subjects like science and mathematics, while humanities may require more discussion-based AfL strategies.

The implications for teaching practice are substantial. Teachers must adopt adaptive strategies, focusing on equitable support for SEND and low-attaining students, while also ensuring that high-attaining students remain engaged. Combining traditional methods with digital tools can create a balanced approach to address the varied needs of a diverse classroom.

This study underscores the importance of professional development to equip teachers with the skills needed to apply these techniques effectively. Further longitudinal research is recommended to assess the long-term impact of formative assessment tools, particularly in fostering sustainable improvements in academic outcomes and teaching practices across diverse educational contexts. By doing so, we can build a more comprehensive understanding of how these strategies can be optimally implemented to meet the evolving demands of modern education.

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